

Simple and complex, sex-specific retinal mosaic in fritillary butterflies

Electronic Supplementary Material

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Table of Contents

Supplement 1: EYESHINE OF <i>Argynnis paphia</i>	2
Supplement 2: Additional electrophysiology	4
Supplement 3: Additional histology	5
Supplement 4: PM Vapour fixation protocol	8
Supplement 5: Phylogeny of simple and complex eyeshine in nymphalids	11

Supplement 1: Eyeshine of *Argynnis paphia*

Figure S1.1. The eyeshine in the central part of the eye of *Argynnis paphia* female (top) and male (bottom). Images were taken in the telemicroscope equipped with a RGB camera and a monochromatic light source. In the female, the eyeshine is bright and uniform between 565 and 615 nm. Further towards red, the tapetum of some ommatidia stops reflecting. In the male, the mosaic is uniform between 615 and 655 nm, the red ommatidia are dark between 510 and 580 nm. The blue-reflecting ommatidia (UU) are present in both sexes; in the male, they only seem to appear dorsally. Lens glare was removed in the male series by subtracting light-adapted images.

Figure S1.2. Colour-boost of *Argynnis paphia* male eyeshine image. An RGB image of the male eyeshine, shown with proper white balance (*left*), and with channel gains and led synth illuminant adjusted (*right*) to better discern the red and yellow ommatidia.

Figure S1.3 Dynamic aspects of the *Argynnis paphia* female eyeshine. *Left*, the eyeshine, after ~20 min dark adaptation. The blue-reflecting ommatidia are likely of the UU type. *Middle*, in a partially bleached eye with less LW rhodopsin, the eyeshine appears brighter, blue ommatidia disappear due to LW metarhodopsin absorption. *Right*, a pseudo-coloured composite of two images taken at 615 nm, after blue and red light preadaptation. The bright cyan ommatidia are likely the UU ommatidia, reacting weakly to blue adaptation light.

Supplement 2: Additional electrophysiology

Figure S2. (a) Variation of spectral sensitivity of G class R1&2 over the retina. *Teal*, sensitivity of G+R- cells in the central retina. *Black*, cells in the ventral retina have an additional peak in the blue, similar to *Heliconius*¹. (b) Spectral sensitivity in female *Speyeria aglaja*. See our previous study for the spectral sensitivity of the male G+R- R1&2 and red R9 receptor².

References to S2

1. McCulloch KJ, Macias-Munoz A, Mortazavi A, Briscoe AD. (2021). Multiple mechanisms of photoreceptor spectral tuning following loss of UV color vision in *Heliconius* butterflies. *BioRxiv*. (doi:10.1101/2021.02.23.432523)
2. Belušič G, Ilić M, Meglič A, Pirih P. (2021). Red-green opponency in the long visual fibre photoreceptors of brushfoot butterflies (Nymphalidae). *Proc Roy Soc B* **288**, 20211560.

Supplement 3: Additional histology

Figure S3.1: The red pigment in the proximal retina of *Argynnis sagana* male. 10 µm thick sections. The classical fixation procedure has likely caused a portion of the pigment to get washed out of the red ommatidia, but one can still classify the ommatidia as red/non-red. Traces of red pigment in the non-red ommatidia are more visible, compared to the semi-thin sections (2 µm) of male *Argynnis paphia* shown in main Fig S3.3. *Scale bar*, 20 µm.

Figure S3.2: The distal retina of male *Argynnis paphia*. Unstained semi-thin (2 μm) sections, 40 \times oil objective. The red pigment clusters in diagonal cells are present in all ommatidia (*left*). Cell boundaries are visible in the phase-contrast image (*middle*) and in the pseudo-coloured image of autofluorescence (*yellow*: blue excitation; blue: UV-excitation). At this level, the traceheolae (cyan) are already thinning out. 40 \times air objective.

Figure S3.3: The proximal retina of male *Argynnis paphia*

top left: brightfield image

top right: phase contrast

bottom left: contrast brightfield

bottom right: fluorescence

Horizontal red pigment clusters are present only in a fraction of ommatidia. The two ommatidial types can be classified also in the phase contrast image, and in the fluorescence image, where the rhabdoms of the non-pigmented ommatidia fluoresce more brightly. Unstained sections (2 μm) observed with 40 \times air objective; excitation: [R,G,B]=[560, 440, 390] nm.

S3.4 Pigments in the distal retina of *Argynnis sagana* female. A series of 10 μm -thick sections. The bright central spots (1) are likely due to the focussing effect of the crystalline cone tip. The four-spotted clusters are likely a part of the pupillary apparatus. The pigmented spots seem to be present in all eight photoreceptors (4), then in six (5-7), then in four (8). The clusters seem to contain both red and brown pigment granules distally (4) and only red pigments proximally (8).

S3.5 Basal retina of *Argynnis paphia* female showing the tapering of the receptors R3-8, the tracheolar baskets between the lobes of the basal R9 receptors, and the fenestrated layer. (a) Pseudo-coloured image. Basal receptor R9, *yellow arrow*; tracheolar basket, *blue arrow*. (b) The source channels, clockwise from *top left*: inverted phase-contrast, colour mapping to (a): *red*; brightfield with stepped-down aperture (*green*); brightfield with open aperture (*blue*); darkfield image (*yellow*). Semithin section (2 μm), imaged with 40 \times air objective.

Supplement 4: PM Vapour fixation protocol

In order to reduce the chance for the eye pigments being lost into the solutions, the standard tissue fixation protocol used in Ljubljana lab was modified by using vapour fixation, by skipping intermediate washout steps, and by shortening the dehydration steps. The change was motivated by our earlier observations that during tissue preparation, either the fixative solution or the alcohol wash would acquire reddish colour, indicative of some pigments being washed out. This should not be surprising, as the ommochrome D, a likely candidate for the red screening pigment in Nymphalids, is water soluble (Figon and Casas, 2018). The protocol was therefore adapted based on the literature describing vapour fixation of freeze-dried samples for immunohistochemical studies.

The butterfly heads were hemisectioned under a stereomicroscope and the eyes were isolated using a razor blade and microscissors. During sectioning, a small drop of fixative was applied to the eye to prevent dessication. The air sacks and the medulla were removed. Sectioned eyes were transferred to a vapour fixation chamber and placed with corneal side facing a piece of filter paper soaked in the fixative (Fig. S4). The chamber was a dessicator vessel (Nz 24/29, Kavalier/Bohemia Glass, Czech Republic) where warm plumes of fixative vapour were flowing over the tissue held at room temperature, simultaneously providing the fixative and preventing dessication. The lid inlet was connected via a silicone tube to the outlet of a washing bottle containing the fixative, placed in a temperature-controlled water bath (Thermo Scientific GP20) at 55 °C. The inlet of the gas-washing bottle was connected to an air pump. The air flow was adjusted to produce a few air bubbles per second. As the fixative vapours were let out of the fixation chamber through an outlet or through a slightly open lid, the process was conducted in a fume hood. After three hours of vapour fixation, the eyes were transferred to vials and dehydrated in graded ethanol series (50 to 100 % in 10% steps), infiltrated in propylene oxide, and embedded in Spurr's resin.

The fixative was a mixture of 3.5 % glutaraldehyde and 4 % formaldehyde in 0.1M Na-cacodylate, buffered at pH 7.2. The embedding medium was Spurr Low-Viscosity Embedding Kit, Sigma-Aldrich, Catalog number EM0300 (formulation ERL 2.05 g, DER 0.715 g, NSA 2.95 g, DMAE 0.05 g).

Figure S4: Vapour fixation apparatus

Table S4: PM Vapour Fixation Protocol

Vapour Fixation	3 hours	3.5 % glutaraldehyde, 4 % formaldehyde, 0.1M Na-cacodylate, pH 7.2, bubbled at 55 °C
Dehydration	8 min	50 % ethanol
	8 min	70 % ethanol
	8 min	80 % ethanol
	8 min	90 % ethanol
(40 min)	8 min	100 % ethanol
Infiltration	15 min	Ethanol : propylene oxide 3:1
	15 min	Ethanol : propylene oxide 1:1
	15 min	Ethanol : propylene oxide 1:3
	15 min	Propylene oxide
(75 min)	15 min	Propylene oxide
Embedding	5 hr	Propylene oxide : Spurr 3:1
	10 hr	Propylene oxide : Spurr 1:1
(1 d)	10 hr	Propylene oxide : Spurr 3:1
	16 hr	Spurr resin (Sigma EM0300) ERL 2.05 g, DER 0.715 g, NSA 2.95 g, DMAE 0.05 g)
(1 d)	3 hr	Spurr resin, open container
Polymerization	16 hr	Oven, heated to 70 °C

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Supplement 5: Phylogeny of simple and complex eyeshine in nymphalids

Figure S5. Phylogenetic occurrence of red receptors across subfamilies of Nymphalidae. Tribes (-ini) and subtribes (-ina) shown in grey were to our knowledge not studied. Phylogeny adapted from Schachat et al.¹

Table S5: Species reported (*indicates own observations; S/ subtribes of Satyrini):

Apaturini	<i>Apatura ilia</i> ^{2,6} , <i>Sasakia charonda</i> ⁶	Limenithidini	<i>Limenithis reducta</i> *
Argynnini	<i>Argynnis paphia</i> ² , <i>A. sagana</i> *, <i>Argyreus hyperbius</i> ³ , <i>Speyeria aglaja</i> ²	Melitacini	<i>Melitaea athalia</i> ²
Charaxini	<i>Charaxes jasius</i> ²	Morphini	<i>Morpho peleides</i> ²
Cyrestini	<i>Cyrestis thyodamas</i> ³	Nymphalini	<i>Polygonia c-aureum</i> ⁶ , <i>P. c-album</i> ⁸ , <i>Vanessa indica</i> ⁷ , <i>V. atalanta</i> ⁷ , <i>V.io</i> *
Danaini	<i>Danaus plexippus</i> ² , <i>Euploea mulciber</i> ³ , <i>Idea leuconoe</i> *, <i>Parantica aglea</i> ³ , <i>P. sita</i> ⁴	Preponiini	<i>Archaeoprepona demophon</i> ²
Elymniini	<i>Bicyclus anyana</i> ⁸	S/Coenonymphina	<i>Coenonympha</i> spp.*
Heliconiini	<i>Agraulis vanillae</i> *, <i>Heliconius erato</i> ²	S/Erebiina	<i>Erebia</i> spp.*
Ithomiini	<i>Greta oto</i> *	S/Maniolina	<i>Maniola jurtina</i> *
Junoniini	<i>Precis almana</i> ³	S/Melanargina	<i>Melanargia galathea</i> *
Kallimini	<i>Hypolimnas bolina</i> ³	S/Parargina	<i>Pararge aegeria</i> ⁸
Libytheinae	<i>Libythea celtis</i> *	S/Satyrina	<i>Brintesia circe</i> *, <i>Hipparchia semele</i> *

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